

The influence of preparation conditions for inorganic-organic nanocomposite layers on their hydrophobicity

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ABSTRACT

Glasses, which are used in architecture, can acquire new properties by functionalization. One of the possible method for functionalization is application of special layers to the glass surface and by this way the glass acquires new properties. One of the most desired properties is hydrophobicity. Wettability is determined mainly by the surface chemistry and surface topography, and it can be modified by the changing of topography such way as the application of inorganic-organic nanocomposite layers. An important method for coating of the materials is sol-gel method. This method presents many advantages such as utilization of simple equipment, high homogeneity of the thin films and the possibility of using an excessive variety of substrates and sizes. Sol-gel is a process in which the features of the layers can be controlled by varying experimental parameters such as process for mixing the reactants and temperature.

In this work, the influence of reactant addition sequence during their mixing and the reaction temperatures on hydrophobicity of layers prepared from sols in "TEOS-TriEOS-H₂O-HNO₃-IPA" system were observed. Simultaneously, the relationship between hydrophobicity of prepared layers and their surface properties was evaluated. The wettability properties of layers were obtained by the measurements of the contact angle of water at room temperature by sessile drop method. The morphological features and surface roughness of the thin layers were obtained by AFM measurements. Moreover, the resistance of prepared layers to water was studied, too.

Keywords: sol-gel, inorganic-organic nanocomposite films, contact angle, AFM, watter corrosion

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